

Serbian Biochemical Society
Eighth Conference
with international participation

University of Novi Sad – Rectorate Hall
16.11.2018. Novi Sad, Serbia

“Coordination in Biochemistry and Life”

Consumption of monoclonal antibodies in Serbia in period 2006-2016

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Monoclonal antibodies are biopharmaceutical drugs, which are used for treatment of cancer, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, asthma, but also some rare diseases such as paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria or the cryopyrin-associated periodic syndromes ¹. Monoclonal antibodies are expensive drugs since they are obtained from cell cultures, mainly mammalian. Based on molecular structure, we differentiate monoclonal antibodies derived from rodents, chimeric antibodies, humanized antibodies, human antibodies and conjugated antibodies (e.g. with radioactive agents).

Data about consumption of these drugs was obtained from website of Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia for 2006 ², and for 2016 ³. The annual consumption was observed in RSD for each individual INN.

During 2006 there was a total of six registered drugs (four different INNs: rituximab, trastuzumab, alemtuzumab, bevacizumab) ². During 2012 alemtuzumab was withdrawn from the market due to undesirable financial profile ⁴. In 2016 fifteen drugs were registered in Serbia. Besides those already registered in 2006, in 2016 we also have cetuximab, panitumumab, brentuximab vedotin, pertuzumab, trastuzumab emtansine, obinutuzumab, nivolumab and pembrolizumab ³. Differences between consumption in 2006 and 2016 are shown in Figure 1. Consumption of only newly registered drugs in 2016 was 429.741.455,30 RSD. Drugs which were registered in both 2006 and 2016 have increased consumption 9.57 times in average.

Result of this descriptive study is insight into number and consumption of monoclonal antibodies in Serbia. Monoclonal antibodies are drugs which have huge potential for expansion of therapeutic use and therefore should be monitored.

Figure 1. Consumption of three drugs in RSD for 2006 (dark) and 2016 (pale).

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (project OI 172058).

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